

BOOK REVIEW

VANDANA SHIVA, “WATER WARS”: PRIVATIZATIONS, POLLUTIONS AND PROFITS, SOUTH END PRESS (2002), CAMBRIDGE MA 02139-4146, PRINTED IN CANADA TRANSCONTINENTAL PRESS.

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The writer Vandana Shiva praised by the guardian as “one of the world’s the most prominent radical scientists” whom provide this book titled as *Water Wars: Privatization, Pollution and Profit*. She holds Doctorate in physics from Punjab University and becomes an internationally recognized environmental scholar and activist in the area of modern environmental concerns. Her career transition from study of physics to ecology was encouraged by the disappearance of Himalayan streams in which she played in childhood age. Here in the preface of this book Shiva quoted Ismail Sergalins² prediction about future wars as the war of the next century will be fought over water. Such projection was explained by Shiva as historical and contemporary global crises reveal that water scarcity and resource disputes are increasingly central to geopolitical tensions. Conflicts between nations such as Israel and Palestine, Ethiopia and Egypt, and Pakistan and India exemplify how access to water can serve as a catalyst for war and sustained regional instability. Shiva suggests the causes made for unequal access of water resource and opposes the deprivation of local communities’ control over water. Interestingly she mentioned the clash of interest made from two paradigm/cultures towards water. These are the ecological paradigm³ and the market paradigm⁴. Unfortunately, commodification of water becomes and continues in conflict with culture of sharing water as free gift. According to Shivas the unsustainable, nonrenewable, and polluting plastic culture is in conflict with civilizations based on soil and mud, and culture of renewal and regeneration. Contemporary global standards and policies by international organization like WTO (The World Trade Organization), IMF (International Monetary Fund) and World Bank towards water access and infrastructure creates both crisis and lacks to mitigate the problem with water occurred globally by providing with international examples. Shiva recommends for these globally

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2 The Vice President of the World Bank in 1995.

3 The ecological paradigm refers a culture sees water as sacred with its provision as a duty for the preservation of life seekers as free gift.

4 The market paradigm refers to a culture sees water as a commodity that can be possible to be owned and traded that was recently flourished corporate culture against water.

growing problems of water through democracy⁵, local and communal control of water as a solution against the ecological terrorism⁶ made by international organizations.

The book contains seven chapters. In chapter one, "*Water Rights: The State, The Market and The Community*" Shiva demonstrated to whom water belongs and rights among different parties including the state, the community and the market. Here Shiva argues how water become loses its communal property to private right under the dominant paradigm of market domination that dictates water to be extracted and traded feely. The historical transformation of water belongingness from riparian system into cowboy economic principle of privatization leads to ownership of water as individual right. This was an application of disregarding the limits of nature's hydrological cycle and the natural rights of others access to water. Here she articulates the systematic ignorance of private interest groups over the communal control of water that promotes community participation as water resource conservation strategy. Thus, water democracy is suggested solution against private ownership of water that promote unsustainable and non-renewable manner of the life ingredient water. The contemporary wave of water privatization gained momentum largely due to Garrett Hardin's 1968 work *The Tragedy of the Commons*, which promoted competition and argued against communal systems of resource management. Finally Shiva identifies the previous recommendation of community control over water shortly refers as "*water democracy*" with nine principles as follows: (1) Water is nature's gift (2) Water is essential to life (3) Life is interconnected through water (4) Water must be free for sustenance needs (5) Water is limited can be exhausted (6) Water must be conserved (7) Water is a commons (8) No one holds a right to destroy (9) Water cannot be substituted. According to Shiva through these basic principles of water democracy co-current depletion and man-made scarcity of water resources would lead to a potential role in undermining global peace could be minimized and solved.

In chapter two, "*Climate Change and the Water Crisis*" Shiva introduced sound explanation on effects of too much and too little of water as a threat to life which is mediated through water in the form of floods, heat waves, cyclones, and droughts. These two extremes are linked to climate change where it's associated with pollution of the atmosphere by the use of fossil fuels and emission of carbon dioxide. Despite this fact the disproportionate contribution of cause of climate change varies throughout countries by which the main victims of disasters are those who had smallest role in creating climate destabilization i.e. coastal communities, small islanders, peasants, and pastoral communities. For this argument Shiva pointed out the sole contributor of climate instability were wealthier region of the world including USA, European Union member states, Russia, China, India, Ukraine, Canada, South Africa, Mexico and Australia. Additionally,

5 Democracy is not merely an electoral ritual but the power of people to shape their destiny, determine how their natural resources are owned and utilized, how their thirst is quenched, how their food is produced and distributed, and what health and education systems they have (Shiva, 2002: p. XV).

6 According to Shiva it is an act of forced apportion of resources from people and denying of sustainable livelihood that causes global warming in the form of terrorism.

the global trade practices by destruction of mangroves in coastal area of India also contributes such environmental imbalances as well as an increase in anthropogenic greenhouse gases emitted largely from industrial and corporate activities also causes enormous losses in our planet. Shiva concludes with a global call with whether water is life-threatening or life-supporting depends to a large extent on the ability of climate justice movements to end atmospheric pollution and to hold unaccountable states and greedy corporations to account.

In chapter three “*The Colonization of Rivers: Dams and Water Wars*” Shiva stated that, unlike to the historical water sharing system of communal control that ensured sustainability and accessibility of water for all, emerging state and private enterprises control over water introduce colonization of rivers for their imperial imperative of commercial benefits. This was undertaken through government control particularly dams were facilitated by giant water project loans from World Bank. Here Shiva illustrated examples especially dams construction in America names as the beginning of dam era highly facilitated the beginning of partnership between government and Private Corporation in control over water. Beyond US border in the systematic operation of *Green Revolution*⁷ dams imposed on the Third World countries through loan conditions were built mainly by the Army Corps. In 1965, despite a severe drought, the United States government refused to supply wheat to India unless the country altered its policies to introduce irrigation-intensive agriculture. Unfortunately, such intensive agricultural practices through dam construction, *Water for Peace* programs left a legacy of centralized water control, violence, hunger, and thirst. This was articulated clearly in the case of India’s Bhakra Dam in Punjab district causing many fatalities both economical and life loses up to 1500 reported killing. Accordingly, water wars emerged due to very man-made floods leads conflicts occurred between Punjab and central government of India.

However, Shiva mentioned as river valley projects are usually considered the solution for agricultural water needs, flood control, and drought mitigation, particularly in the case of India the return from this large investment has been far lower than anticipated. Nevertheless, such damming faces protest from women, peasants, and tribal whose life-support systems of many families disrupted with displacement and whose sacred sites have been threatened. Against such threat massive population movements managed but ineffective due to the systematic practices of World Bank in water control projects make complex the search of solution for the needy. Because World Bank and indebted governments, who facilitated such wild deals with corporation to own, control, distribute and sell water resources. Finally this chapter also discussed with the global picture of displacement, how river diversions causes water wars, the incidence of hydro-jihad between Türkiye, Syria and Iraq where dam was became power that used as means of political control, the case of conflict between Israel and the West Bank as an act of water apartheid that applies ethnic and religious lines as means of denying equal access of water, the recent conflict over Nile and

7 Great increase in the production of food grains especially wheat and rice against indigenous agricultural practices.

lastly assess international water rules that lack to respond the ecological and political challenges posed by water conflict discussed in details.

In chapter four “*The World Bank, WTO and Corporate control over water*” Shiva claims as giant water projects and dams were benefiting the powerful funding agents including their construction companies, industries, corporations, and commercial farms but also dispossess the weak. Among the powerful agents of privatization of water World Bank was used as an instrument for corporate control of water in all states in the world. Here Shiva mentioned as the systematic operation of World Bank was not only in resulting water scarcity and pollution for communities’ but also uses loan conditions as a strategy to turn water scarcity into a market opportunity for private companies’ involvement in water trade. Public–private partnership model promoted by World Bank injects billions of dollars as credit to the third world countries in attracting private capital that used as a subsidy for water market companies. Shiva argued that the World Bank water privatization model resulted erosion of water right against public democratic right of water, limitation of livelihood and shrinks employment rights for those who work in local water sanitation system.

Shiva in this chapter mentioned as the common precondition for the World Bank and IMF to demand water deregulation as part of their lending conditions. An explicit example of this phenomenon mentioned by Shiva was IMF’s loans disbursed through the International Finance Corporation in requirements for partial or full privatization of water supply and insisted on policy creation to stimulate “*full cost recovery*” and eliminate subsidies. In order to qualify, for loans, the case in African governments increasingly submitted with water privatization pressures. Most likely the emergency of world trade organization (WTO), the general agreement on trade in services (GATS) along with World Bank and IMF the global control of economy existed. One of the global resources became under the control of GATS through free trade principles was “*water*” with other agricultural, intellectual properties and investments. Here, Shiva with concrete facts and descriptions explores such organizations and international agreements effects on water as: results hijacking of common resources, price hikes, environmental pollutions, costs public liberty, undermining cultural practices of indigenous knowledge’s i.e. democratic decentralization of water control by the community, most importantly resulting scarcity of water for the public. *It is upsetting to read what Shiva describes in this chapter about the “great thirst” in Mexico-how human-made interventions have created severe water scarcity, forcing babies and children to drink Coca-Cola and Pepsi. It is truly shocking!* In response to such disparities caused by privatization of water public protests and grievances especially in Bolivia presented as an illustrative example that indicates water wars between corporation and citizens.

In chapter five “*Food and Water*” Shiva articulate the compatible correlation of water and food production for which people in different part of the world develop their own culture of food production (i.e. Asia’s rice production, Ethiopian Teff farming and Pastoral cultivations) along with water productivity unlike to the green revolution focused on labor productivity. However

impressive yields of food production emerged through labor productivity unfortunately low organic matter and moisture conservation capacity of the soil diminished. Such phenomenon is the result of water intensive production of the industrial agriculture. According to Shiva most recently emerged “*Green Revolution*” replaced indigenous agriculture with monocultures, where dwarf varieties replaced tall ones, chemical fertilizers substituted organic ones, and irrigation displaced rain fed cropping. As a result, soils were deprived of vital organic material, and soil moisture droughts became recurrent. This entire counter results attached with water crisis occurred by industrial cultivation featured with unsustainable agriculture. It’s aligned to agricultural culture of water waste and destruction indorsed by previously mention international organizations i.e. World Bank, IMF, WTO, and GATS. However, such an unsustainable mode of industrial agriculture was responsible for many fatalities among the populations of Third World countries, and women were disproportionately affected, as Shiva argues in Chapter Five.

In Chapter Six, “Converting Scarcity into Abundance,” unlike the introduction—which discusses how water crises emerge by turning abundance into scarcity—Shiva treats both “scarcity” and “abundance” as products of water culture. Through the case of India, she proposes recommendations for water conservation as well as exit strategies from global water wars. That was indigenous culture of ancient water conservation technology. The first indigenous practice identified was the regeneration of water-cycle systems through careful observation of rainfall and its patterns. The second was the application of traditional water-management systems that assign both rights and responsibilities to community members. The third was the use of decentralized water democracies. Finally, people’s alternatives for sustainability needed to be established. Shiva concludes this chapter as follows:

“Man-made water scarcity and ubiquitous water conflicts can be minimized with the recognition of water as a common resource. Water conservation movements are also showing that the real solution to the water crisis lies in people’s energy, labor, time, care, and solidarity. The blueprints provided by people’s movements have shown the possibility of creating abundance out of scarcity” (V, Shiva, p. 127-8)

In chapter seven “*The Sacred Waters*” Shiva confirms her propounded believe in ecological paradigm that sees water as sacred with its provision as a duty for the preservation of life. But the modern market paradigm insisted that we forget its sacredness through technical provision of water through pipes and luxuries packed bottles and glass. She revealed varieties of religious culture towards wager sacredness like under Rigvedic cosmology of the god of rain, Hindu mythology of Gangs River, Holy Quran verses of Islam and Christianity ritual of baptism. And she finally mentioned the commodification of water reduces its value only to its commercial values. Due to this the spiritual, ecological, cultural, and social significance of resources like water was eroded like forests as timber mines, minerals as raw materials. Such monetary and commercial pricing of water resulted water crisis globally. Shiva concludes to be free from such potential global crisis

resources like water can often have very high value while having no price. Thus, protection of vital resources like water cannot be ensured through market logic alone. It demands a recovery of the sacred and a recovery of the commons that enable us to save and share water, and convert scarcity into abundance.

“*Water Wars*” of Vandana Shiva undoubtedly fantastic in helping me adhering the global water crisis with potential source of global war now and the future. And also, it helps me to grasping Environmental Sociology with specific issues of water within the globe. What makes the book fantastic were well integrated views of international, national, regional, local level analysis of water crisis all over the world. Additionally, it was also saturated with legal, economic, religious, historical, socio-cultural, and political aspects of water compiled by Shiva. Then shortly I labeled Shiva as “A Water Activist”. But due to the modern economic system dominance in all aspects of life, her recommendation of complete communal control of water would be questionable.